

THE INFLUENCE OF INFORMATION AND COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGIES ON THE EDUCATION OF STUDENTS IN THE CONDITIONS OF MODERN GLOBALIZATION

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Abstract. *In this article, modern information in the process of globalization, which affects the consciousness and education of students during their educational activities, through the use of information technologies in the educational system and interactions in society, focuses on its achievements and specific shortcomings, the impact of information on students is increasing, it is within a limited scope. it can range from psychological effects to complete personality change (internet addiction, computer software mania, hacker syndrome). They show ways to determine the negative effects of information technologies on the personality of students, the factors affecting their education and their elimination, and the ways to study the optimal conditions for using these technologies in the educational process.*

Keywords: *globalization, information, Internet, hacking, virtual world, computer technology, Internet networks, mobile phone, telecommunications, information technologies, information resources, ideological attacks, mass media, immorality, protection from propaganda of violence, education, information culture, radio, television.*

At a time when computer games and attractions created on the basis of virtual world technologies have a great influence on the minds of modern youth, we should not forget that people can communicate with computers in unfamiliar situations through the use of mobile phones, animated films, credit and plastic cards. In addition, the close interaction of teachers themselves with information technology opens up opportunities to expand their influence.

When using modern information technologies in the educational process, teachers should pay special attention to the following situations.

First, news that may occur in the field of information technology is transferred to traditional communication settings. There is an increase in requirements for accuracy, consistency, consistency and reflexivity of conducted pedagogical and psychological research. Here the role of psychic mediums is reduced.

Secondly, feedback increases. The characteristics of traditional activities are computerized. There is a “humanization” of software and hardware intended for the educational process, including for young children. In them, users fill their activities with elements that do not exist, but which are necessary to perform some actions. Such possible situations form a complex situational structure of various forms of activity related to information technology (including activities related to learning) [5].

The impact of modern information technologies on students is increasing and can range from a limited psychological impact to a complete change in personality (Internet addiction, computer program mania, hacker syndrome). To date, the issue of complete personality

transformation has not been studied in detail by scientists. Therefore, the active participation of teachers and psychologists in the process of development and implementation of modern information technologies intended for the educational process is necessary. They study the optimal conditions for using these technologies in the educational process, as well as issues related to identifying and eliminating the negative impact of information technologies on the personality of students.

President Sh.M. Mirziyoyev about trust in the “Youth Union” and the opportunities it creates, demanding that they be fully prepared for the future of the country, said: “We consider all the youth of Uzbekistan to be the decisive force of our country and society, and you are always such a great leader our people. We believe that you will be worthy of his trust” [1].

Today, one of the necessary needs of all young people is to study information technology. For example, Internet technologies cause positive changes in human education, based on changes in the quality of communicative and cognitive activity and changes in teaching methods. Because when working with the Internet, student activity increases, the educational process is individualized, the authoritarian relationship between teacher and student decreases, and it becomes possible to work with different sources of information (which may be mutually contradictory or mutually exclusive). This will promote the personality development of the students. They are encouraged to think independently, take initiative and be mobile. However, there may also be negative consequences.

Intensive intellectual and creative development cannot ensure students' adaptation to the existing social environment. They can be connected to various computer resources, including the Internet. This may cause the person to be separated from others in the future. There may be sudden changes in the psyche of children, the replacement of friends with heroes of the virtual world, a decrease in mental reactions, and a narrowing of interests. In addition, it is important for scientists to find out which mental components, obtained under the influence of modern information technologies, move into the sphere of activity “without computers” and the mechanisms of the impact of informatization of education on the psyche. This, in turn, is considered one of the most pressing issues for teachers.

Educators who use information technology in the educational process emphasize that educational activities will change due to such qualities as accuracy, efficiency and predictability. Correctly explaining the situation and teaching students to consciously choose the optimal way to solve problems becomes the main task of teachers. E-mail, chats, teleconferences require written communication skills (which have been practically forgotten in developed countries due to the development of telephone communications). This includes familiarity with the Internet, the culture of business and personal correspondence, and the study of special signs that express mood.

The Internet raises international communication to a new level, activates universal knowledge, and creates conditions for intensive learning of foreign languages during correspondence. Freeing a person from excessive and hard work and preparing conditions for his development based on the use of information technologies in various fields of activity entails the loss of some skills and qualifications. For example, the importance of spreadsheets today cannot be denied. They help people get rid of a lot of unnecessary work. However, the use of calculators even in elementary grades can cause them to lose oral language and counting skills. As a result, students will not be able to perform number concept operations correctly.

In the current conditions of unprecedented speed of information exchange, “centers” in the West are trying to spread the “attractions” of Western life, including the influence of “mass culture” in the form of “breaths of freedom” among other countries. and people. In particular, American television programs and films account for three-quarters of the global market. His popular music, American study habits, food habits and even their clothing are imitated all over the world.” [2]

At the same time, examples of “mass culture”, various information technologies, radio television, and social networks on the Internet are cleverly used.

First President I.A. Karimov said: “If we look at history, strong countries used to openly oppress weak countries and impose their opinions on them, but towards the end of the 20th century such policies took a new form. Today, in order to achieve their goals, powerful states and individual political centers are trying to subjugate the minds of the people of countries under their influence. [3]

The negative impact of the rapid development of information media on the education of young people in the context of modern globalization is shown below.

Firstly, as a result of the high development of mass media, the Internet, mobile phone, telecommunications and various news publications have entered.

Secondly, the widespread dissemination of various forms of “mass culture” among young people. They manifest themselves mainly in clothing, behavior, spending free time, dulling of tastes, and attitude towards national values.

Thirdly, cases such as imitation and blind adherence to Western ideals are also observed among young people. At the same time, it is not difficult to notice that moral and spiritual models widespread abroad are absorbed into the consciousness of young people through cinema, fashion and various advertising.

Unfortunately, in most cases, the principle of gradually depriving young people of national identity, attacking their national traditions and customs, respecting their historical memory and thereby achieving dominance over nations is gaining strength. The idea of globalization is one of the most pressing issues at the moment, but it is interpreted in different ways. He has his supporters and opponents. Despite the fact that this process is openly and covertly opposed, it is growing and therefore requires special attention.

Globalization comes from the words globe, global and global. It should be noted that globalization, according to most experts, means increased economic integration. From this point of view, it is concluded that “globalization occurs within the framework of economic relations.” Because globalization is a concept directly related to all aspects of life, including human spirituality. For this reason, some encyclopedias note that the term "global" problems refer to problems that are diverse in scale and scope and concern the entire globe and humanity. [9]

Today we are witnessing the fact that globalization has manifested itself in all spheres of public life and has become a particularly sharp weapon of ideological influence.

In essence, globalization in the field of information is a process that creates great opportunities for society, for the interaction of people in all parts of the world, for the acquisition of scientific and cultural values. But we must not forget that there are also negative aspects of information globalization. Ideas that arise in one region or country quickly spread throughout the world. As a result, humanity constantly feels pressure from various ideological centers serving the interests of certain countries and political forces, spreading from distant and close sources. In such

a situation, a person who does not have his own independent opinion, established beliefs, strong will and worldview cannot resist ideological pressures that sometimes manifest themselves openly and sometimes secretly. Today, ideological attacks on our society from outside have not stopped. It should be noted that the majority of the audience of global network users are young people, and most of the Internet content consists of information aimed at poisoning their consciousness and worldview with ideas of foreign content. In particular, our youth, who approach their lives with a passion for their profession, for the future, go to sites in the hope of receiving positive information, and as a result, without our knowledge, the functioning of various social networks, forums, dating sites quickly attract young people. Currently, the Internet offers a wide range of opportunities for young people speaking different languages. In particular, the growing audience of mobile Internet users creates ample opportunities for openly receiving information of various contents. And imitative teenagers are becoming more and more interested in it and trying to use it more. As a result, the global network, currently emerging in the context of the information revolution, is of serious concern to society. They create their own society, and these societies call themselves “cyber-international NET”, “children of the Internet”, “citizens of the Internet (netizens)”. [9]

They enter the political field as an international cyber association, uniting young people through the Internet and opposing official communications from government bodies. We urge all young people who are just starting out in life to be aware: “We fully support the desire of our people to make wider use of the capabilities of the Internet. Although it is repeated, we would like to say that we do not like to build some kind of wall in the world of information, withdraw into our shell and face restrictions. At the same time, if we take into account the events taking place around us today, in remote regions, we should not take into account that malicious forces aimed at misleading young people who have not yet formed their consciousness and life views are also trying to use the capabilities of the Internet in their interests, and how such efforts can lead to negative consequences. This cannot be done,” he says.

Although the Internet is a great achievement of mankind and has created great opportunities in our lives today, it is no secret that this miracle is a tool of powerful ideological influence and causes serious problems. Information-cultural and information-ideological expansion carried out through global telecommunication networks and the media is causing concern in different countries of the world. The possibility of becoming dependent and losing independence in the future worries state leaders, public institutions and citizens. Even now, many countries are forced to take special measures to protect their culture, traditions and spiritual values from the influence of foreign information. In this regard, it should be noted that in many countries around the world, regulatory documents have been adopted to protect the population, especially young people, from negative influence of the Internet.

Today, higher educational institutions and their branches in the regions, all educational institutions in our country are connected to the national educational network “ZiyoNET” and high-speed Internet, which indicates the scale of work done in this direction.

At the same time, in order to create an entertaining information space for young people and ensure the information security of minors, further improving the educational and information portal “ZiyoNET”, increasing its organizational, technical and interactive capabilities, integrating modern Internet resources, social services popular among youth and developing games, the necessary measures are taken to develop applications and include them in the educational programs of educational institutions.

It is very important to be critical of information received from the Internet and expand your understanding of the world based on its useful sources, be able to refute biased information, form ideological immunity, and not be indifferent to modern political and economic trends. [7]

Information security protects minors from destructive ideas that deprive them of faith, sacred ideals and beliefs, directly affecting them. Therefore, the need for information security, first of all, is directly related to the individual and society, the individual and the state, and the individual. and its integrity, nation and national values, including customs, traditions, historical and cultural heritage, continuity of generations, as well as the presence of destructive ideas that have a moral impact on the values associated with the nation's perspective.

If the information security of minors is not respected and effective measures are not taken against them, destructive ideas will inevitably lead to the genocide of historically existing peoples and nations through the destruction of national values. Unfortunately, people with evil goals attract young children and adolescents to these types of games through various social networks, including As a result, children become "dolls" in this game and even commit suicide. Prevention of such situations and the safety of children remains an urgent problem. However, the need for information networks is growing day by day.

It is worth noting that from the first days of independence, the leader of our country made it a priority policy of our country to educate young people so that they become people who deeply understand the world and keep up with the times. The formation of an information culture in them occupies a special place among the issues of educating promising youth. Since the formation of information culture is directly related to the development of society, this is an issue of social significance at the national level. Therefore, in the conditions of the formation of the information society, the study of all aspects of the information process is of particular importance.

In the national segment of the Internet, sites are hosted in such areas as Hi-Tech, culture, science, sports, business, government intelligence services, new types of services are being introduced, which is the reason for the increase in the number of users. An example of this is that the number of Internet users in Uzbekistan has exceeded 10 million.

In conclusion, we note that every young person enters society along with the acquisition of a perfect profession and the competent use of the media. It is the sacred duty and responsibility of parents and all educators to ensure that standards are observed with the information received by all in accordance with the interests of the individual and the laws of society.

REFERENCES

1. Мирзиёев Ш.М. «Стратегия действий» по пяти приоритетным направлениям развития Республики Узбекистан. -Т., Узбекистан, 2017. «Газета. длинная"
2. Каримов И. Выступление А. Халка на внеочередной сессии Хорезмского областного Совета народных депутатов // Народная вода. - 2012. - 10 октября.
3. Каримов И.А. Свободная и благополучная Родина, свободная и благополучная жизнь – наша цель. Том 8, - Т: Узбекистан, 2000. - Б. 491.
4. Каримов И.А. Высокая духовность – неиссякаемая сила. -Т.: Духовность. 2008 г.
5. Закон «Об основах государственной политики в отношении молодежи в Республике Узбекистан». Уведомление № 2 от 1992 г. Статья 80.
6. Закон Республики Узбекистан "О гарантиях и свободе информации" Бюллетень 1997 г. № 4 Статья 108.

7. Информационно-коммуникационные технологии: актуальные вопросы правового регулирования. Журнал "Демократизация и права человека". - Т.: 2009. #2
8. Моминов А. Узбекистан: На пути к информированному обществу.-Т.: Турон замин зиё.2013г.
9. Чернов А.А. Становление глобального информационного общества: проблемы и перспективы. - М.: Издательско-торговая корпорация "Дашков и К". -2003.-С 18.
10. Худайкулов Х.Ж. Влияние информационных и коммуникационных технологий на обучающихся в эпоху глобализации. Современный обучения. Журнал №4 -Т.: 2020 г.
11. Высокая правовая культура – основа демократического общества // Народное слово. - 2013. - 25 января.
12. Домен «UZ»: развитие и перспективы // Народное слово. - 2012. - 2 мая.
13. Национальный форум прессы Узбекистана // Народное слово. - 2013. - 20 ноября
14. Электронный сервис — это быстро, просто и экономически эффективно // Люди; слово - 2012. - 14 марта.
15. Современные информационно-коммуникационные технологии играют важную роль в совершенствовании деятельности средств массовой информации // Люди; слово - 16 марта 2012 г.